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technical expert from another country who speaks a different language and lives by different values. Still, it is expected of us to be successful in working with “the other side”. There are various requirements for successful interaction in a multicultural environment; the importance of self-awareness and attitude is often underestimated.[2]

Extra-linguistic and paralinguistic issues Linguistic issues An individual’s attitude shapes their habits and behavior. And group behavior ultimately influences an organization’s culture.

So, to improve your culture, you must first focus on changing people’s attitudes.

Rituals lie in the center of the core belief systems of the people who practice them.

Rituals bring about a sense of group identity, and therefore strengthen and build community Habit is ???

A routine of behavior that is repeated regularly and tends to occur subconsciously

Fixed way of thinking, willing, or feeling acquired through previous repetition of a mental experience Defined from the standpoint of psychology

The most interesting customs around the world.[3]

[1] <https://www.communicationtheory.org/cross-cultural-communication/>

<https://www.linkedin.com/pulse/importance-attitude-cross-cultural-communication-tilman-rieger>

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reference

[2][https:// azkurs.org/ subj ect--cultural- comm unicati on -topic-extra-lin gui sti c- issues.html](https://azkurs.org/subject--cultural-communication-topic-extra-linguistic-issues.html)

[3][https://www.linkedin.com/pulse/impo r- tance-attitude-cross-cultural- communication-tilman-rieger](https://www.linkedin.com/pulse/importance-attitude-cross-cultural-communication-tilman-rieger)